

Speculation on an Energy Requirement Necessary for It to Lorentz Transform

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 17, 2024

From special relativity it is known that energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. What then are the requirements for such an energy? It seems that it exists in space-time and is measurable, but we ask is that enough? We note that if one has two masses m_1, m_2 then each transforms as the fourth component, but so does the sum. We suggest, however, that in such a case, m_1+m_2 may physically exist, but each piece m_1 and m_2 also without the other present, i.e. all of these energies are standalone.

In other words, we suggest that given energy in a certain region of space (if it is unchanging in time), one cannot simply assume that this energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector unless this energy may exist uncoupled on its own. For example, mathematically one could have $M = a_1 + a_2$. M could be the rest mass of an electron. One may have energy pieces $a_1 + a_2$ which as a sum transform as $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ without transforming themselves as $a_1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $a_2/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ if they are not standalone energies. If each may exist as a standalone energy, then each should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

In particular, we consider the example of the electrostatic energy $.5e_0 \int dv E \cdot E$ (E =electric field) confined to a region outside a uniformly charged sphere. This must represent physical energy in space, but this energy cannot exist by itself. It is coupled to the sphere and so the requirement is looser. Indeed, $.5 e_0 \int E \cdot E dv$ both inside and outside the uniformly charged sphere is not standalone and not the full self-energy and the sum need not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector as is the case.

We argue that $\sum dq_i \phi_i$, i.e. the work needed to bring in charges to create the uniformly charged sphere is not all of the work present. Once a charge reaches the surface of the growing sphere, it must be held in place, say by a spring whose potential energy changes. This does not happen in a separable, standalone, manner. Thus, one should incorporate both energies. Why is this not done? We argue that there is a specific reason, namely that one focuses on electrostatic work in order to find the energy in the electric field outside of the sphere which is a physical observable. Overall, it is only the entire energy of this coupled system which represents mass, i.e. transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector as shown by Fermi in 1922 (1) and also discussed by Feynman (2). The point we wish to make is that it seems that any non-standalone sum of energies need not transform piece by piece as the fourth component of a 4-vector. It seems that it is too restrictive to assume that each coupled energy piece must transform as the fourth component.

Special Relativity and Energy

Special relativity suggests that energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. If one has standalone energies m_1 and m_2 , each transforms as the fourth component, as does the sum m_1+m_2 . We point out, however, that breaking the sum into pieces may be done numerically, but might not have physical meaning if the two pieces do not represent standalone physical systems. One may in fact consider the possible situation that $M_{unboosted} = a_1 + a_2$ and that $M_{boosted} = M/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but that a_1 and a_2 do not necessarily transform as

$a_1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $a_2/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. As long as a_1 and a_2 are not standalone systems, this does not seem to be a problem, we suggest.

As a somewhat related example, consider a rest mass m_0 which is boosted to $m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. Here m_0 and v are now intertwined in a nonadditive manner, but mathematically one may write this as the sum $m_0cc + b$. If the mass is boosted a second time, then:

$$\left| \begin{matrix} g_2 & g_2v_2 \\ g_2v_2 & g_2 \end{matrix} \right| \left| \begin{matrix} m_0 & g_1 v_1 \\ m_0 g_1 & v_1 \end{matrix} \right| \longrightarrow \text{energy} = g_2g_1 v_1 m_0 + g_2g_2v_2 m_0 \quad ((1)) \quad c=1$$

If one used m_0cc+b , one would expect to see a physical piece $m_0 g(v_1+v_2)$, but that is not what appears in ((1)). Here $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/c}$.

We suggest that the condition that coupled energies may not transform as fourth components of 4-vectors is found in electrostatics.

Electrostatic Self-Energy

Electrostatic self-energy is often calculated using:

$$\text{Electrostatic self-energy} = \sum \text{over } i \text{ } \phi_i(q \text{ partial}) dq \quad ((2))$$

Here one builds up a charge distribution, say a uniformly charged sphere where $q \text{ partial}$ represents the growing core. The point we make is that ((2)) is not the total self energy as a charge reaching the growing sphere must be "fastened" in place by say a spring. The spring stretches to create force and this represents potential energy in addition to $q \phi_i$. Feynman calls the spring a "rubber band" (2). The fastening and electrostatic energies should not be separated as each cannot exist as a separate system on its own.

This begs the question: Why is ((2)) used then? It is as if there is no spring in the expression for ((2)). We argue that ((2)) is essential for finding an expression for the energy in the electric field outside the sphere (as well as inside). In particular, there is no "rubber band" outside the sphere. The field energy outside the sphere is a physical energy which may be useful in problems and so it is good to be able to compute it, but it is part of a coupled system of energies and so does not need to transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. This energy cannot stand on its own.

We consider the case of a uniformly charged sphere.

$$\text{Electrostatic piece of self-energy ignoring spring} = \int_{(0,R)} d^3r \int_{(0,R)} d^3r' \frac{1}{r-r'} \rho(r) \rho(r') \quad ((3))$$

Note that the integral ranges from $r=0$ to $r=R$ and so does not describe the region outside of the sphere. It may, however, be shown using Gauss' law that ((2)) is equivalent to:

$$.5e_0 \int \text{all volume} E \cdot E \, dv \quad \text{over all volume, i.e. outside and inside the sphere} \quad ((4))$$

Outside the sphere $= \frac{1}{2} \int_{R}^{\infty} k \frac{dq}{r^2} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{R}^{\infty} \frac{kQ}{r^2} dr = \frac{kQ}{2R}$

Inside the sphere: $\frac{1}{2} \int_{0}^{R} k \frac{dq}{r^2} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{0}^{R} \frac{kQ r^3}{r^2} dr = \frac{kQ}{10}$ ((5))

Using $k = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0}$ one finds that ((3)) = ((4)) + ((5))

Thus, the expression $\int dq \phi$ evaluated for $r=0$ to $r=\infty$ is equivalent to a field energy equation which holds inside and outside the sphere. Outside the sphere there are no “rubber bands” holding the charges together, so this should be total physical energy in that region.

Thus, the advantage of ((2)) is that it leads to an expression for energy in the electric field outside of the sphere.

Inside the sphere, however, electrostatic energy is combined with a “rubber band” energy (2) and this changes as each piece of dq is added and so the two should not really be decoupled.

Apparent Problem

If one only considers the field energy, then in the rest frame one has:

Field self-energy = $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int dv E \cdot E$ ((6a))

While in the moving frame:

Field self-energy = $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int dv E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 \int dv B \cdot B$ ((6b))

here E is the electric field and B , the magnetic.

If one performs an expansion using $v \ll c$, then the energy in the moving frame is not

$\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int dv E \cdot E$ (rest frame) for the electromagnetic field ((7))

((7)) should apply if the field rest energy $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E dv$ transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

We argue that this is fine because it should be the total energy which represents electromagnetic mass energy which transforms as the fourth component. In other words, $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E dv$ is not electromagnetic rest mass and neither is ((7)) $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E dv$.

Overall, one must consider the effects of the “rubber band” so that one obtains an overall electromagnetic rest mass which indeed transforms as:

$$M_0 \text{ (electromagnetic, } c=1) \rightarrow M_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((8))$$

This is explicitly shown by Fermi (1922) (1) in which he uses a Coulomb force as the “rubber band” force and shows that electromagnetic mass is:

$$\frac{4}{3} \text{ electromagnetic energy} - \frac{1}{3} \text{ electromagnetic energy} \quad ((9))$$

The second term in ((9)) arises from the Coulomb piece. As a result, even though $\int E \cdot E \, dv$ represents physical energy in the region outside of the sphere and electromagnetic energy within the sphere, it does not transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector because it is not the total energy and it cannot exist on its own without the “rubber band” Coulomb force. Rest mass represents inertia and if one is interested in the electromagnetic rest mass of an electron, for example, one cannot ignore the “rubber band”. Furthermore, neither the “rubber band” energy or the electromagnetic one can stand on their own and so each piece does not need to transform as the fourth component, but rather the overall rest mass of the electron.

By pulling out ((6a)) and ((6b)) and having it represent a piece of the rest mass of the electron, one cannot guarantee that this piece transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector because this energy cannot exist on its own like $M=m_1+m_2$, where m_1 and m_2 are both standalone masses.

One may further note that the electromagnetic energy $\int dq \, \phi$ is only computed for $r=0$ to $r=R$ and is not the self-energy because it ignores the “rubber” band energy. The presence of energy outside the sphere only appears when one converts the internal integral $\int dq \, \phi$ into one which exists in all of space, i.e. $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \int E \cdot E \, dv$ (for the rest frame).

Conclusion

In general, given a piece of rest mass M , one may divide it into pieces m_1 and m_2 such that $M=m_1+m_2$. In such a case, M , m_1 and m_2 all transform as the fourth component of a Lorentz 4-vector because all are standalone examples of rest mass.

In the case that one has energy which is not standalone, i.e. depends on other energies in the system, then one cannot immediately require that it transform as the fourth component of a Lorentz 4-vector, it seems. In particular, if one wishes to find the rest mass of the electron, it may be associated with two standalone parts: an electromagnetic piece and a non-electromagnetic one because it is possible to have an uncharged particle. The electromagnetic piece, however, is not: $\int dq \, \phi$ because this excludes the energy of the “rubber band” which holds the charges together. One cannot simply calculate the energy of bringing in charge pieces to assemble a spherical ball of charge because each piece must be held and this requires energy (i.e. stretching of a spring). It seems that the reason one considers $\int dq \, \phi$ by itself is to convert it into an integral involving the electric field, which exists in all of space. Thus: $\int dq \, \phi = \int_{\text{Internal sphere}} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \, dv + \int_{\text{region outside of the sphere}} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \, dv$. Outside of the sphere there is no rubber band, but neither piece is standalone and both depend on the “rubber band”. Thus, we argue that one cannot

expect that this field energy (which is not the full electromagnetic rest mass in the rest frame) should transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Rather, the whole rest mass should, which it does as shown by Fermi (1922, (2)).

In particular, if one has a rest mass m_0 , it is expected to transform as $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$). It may be possible, however, to write $m_0 = a_1+a_2$ such that the sum transforms as $(a_1+a_2)/\sqrt{1-v^2}$, but a_1 and a_2 do not by themselves because they are not standalone energies. This seems to be what happens in the case of electromagnetic field energy which is not fully electromagnetic mass. (2)

References

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